
THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SHAPING YOUTH BEHAVIOR IN SELECTED COUNCILS OF FCT, ABUJA

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ABSTRACT	KEY WORDS
<p>This study, the “Influence of Social Media among youth in Abuja Municipal Area and Bwari Area Councils of FCT, Abuja” was carried out to investigate the way social media influences the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of FCT, Abuja. The study adopted quantitative survey design with the questionnaire used as the research instrument for data collection. Data collected was analyzed using descriptive method while univariate frequency distribution tables, percentages and SPSS were used as statistical tools for data collection. Finding of the study revealed that social media platforms are used among the youth to a great extent as majority of them make use of the platforms at least more than twice a day. In the use of the platforms, Facebook endears the youth more for use compared to other social media platforms. The use of social media, therefore, influences the behaviour of youth to a great extent by making them cultivate the habit of living a flamboyant lifestyle. Finding however, revealed that the use of social media is challenged majorly by high data charges from the network providers followed by poor network, while unstable power and activities of Internet scammers are other challenges in the use of the social media among the youth. The recommended that policy makers should benefit from the youth’s interest in the social media in general and the Facebook in particular by using the platforms in reaching out to them (youth) on relevant policies/programmes that can impact positively on their lives in particular and the society in general. It further charged the youth to dedicate more time on the social media for the activities beneficial to them rather than merely posting personal photos and videos which have minimal impacts on their lives. The study concluded that social media is used among the youth and its utilization by this group of the people has tremendous impact on their behavior</p>	<p>social media, youths, Abuja municipal, Bwari area council, FCT</p>

INTRODUCTION

Media influence is one of the most researched areas in communication and media studies. Consequently, the use of social media and its influence on different group of users has globally become a topical subject for public discourse and debate. Indeed, the transformation in the technology of information and communication generation, processing, storage and dissemination witnessed in the 21st century unprecedentedly opened-up new media platforms unmatched in history in terms of interconnectedness, interactivity, multiplicity and accessibility (Adaja & Ayodele, 2013; Dourish, 2001; Fab-Ukozor, & Ojiakor, 2020).

The new media, that resulted from the invention, encapsulated the characteristics of the old or traditional media, and extended the potentials and possibilities into which both the “old” and “new” media could be put into use. The new media, promoted by Internet technology, exhibit an integration and convergence of the existing media to extend the frontiers of the possibilities of the media of communication. The new media, which hallmarked the integration and convergence of computer and telecommunication technologies, revolutionized the face of human communication especially in the 21st century. The new information Technology “provides near limitless possibilities of increasing the quantity and enhancing the quality, speed, and availability of information in a complex but increasingly interdependent world ...” (Adaja, & Ayodele, 2013).

The new media, propelled and driven by the Internet, provide platforms for social interactions between and among users in such a manner that no older platforms/media can boast of. The new media display such potentials that the only limitation to the dynamism is ignorance or illiteracy in terms of the ability to use the hardware and/or software for maximum effects in the realm of communication, education, politics, economics, social or technology (Adaja, & Ayodele, 2013). In his opinion:

Social Media has indeed; become a trending lexicon in media study such that many researchers have turned towards investigating and evaluating its impact and effect on society lately. This is so as several decades saw the dominance of the conventional (traditional) media in society especially in exercising the responsibility of information, education and entertainment. But with the turn of events in the new century, the evolution of technology and the ubiquitous power of the information and communication technology (ICT) which has converged the world so much so that Marshall McLuhan’s(1962) global village philosophy was no longer a mere expression but a startling reality (Agbawe, 2018, p. 18):

This position has become too obvious that Kaplan & Haenlein (2001) note that the current trend toward social media can therefore be seen as an evolution back to the internet’s root, since it retransforms the World Wide Web to what it was initially created for: a platform to facilitate information exchange between users. A group of online communication channels that allow individuals, groups, governments, organizations, and companies etc. to share information, ideas and express their selves via virtual networks sites, social media have succeeded in connecting individuals so that they have been able to share information and connect with each other without any boundaries (Agbawe, 2018; Al Saud & Khan, 2013; Boateng & Amankwaa, 2016; Green, et al. 2018; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010; Mohsin, 2020; Nkordeh, Oni, Olowononi & Bob-Manu, 2017; Oyetunde, 2017; Schaefer, 2011; Sorensen, Ponas, Hayikhani & Hayar, 2014; Tayo, Adebola & Yahya, 2019; Vishranti & Prafulla, 2016; Wilson, 2018). In his words:

Virtual platforms popularly and professionally known as social media are known for the facilitation of information sharing, enlightenment and the enhancement of development issues across the globe regardless of distance and time, which is the regular side. The popular believe today is that mankind has been exposed to simpler and better ways of exhibiting things with the aid of technology. In both contemporary and primitive societies today, most

people utilize these platforms to interrelate with physical, virtual friends and connect with old friends, share thoughts, ideas and feelings effectively and efficiently within a short period of time (Wilson, 2018, p. 262).

Research Questions

1. What are the social media platforms often used by youths in Abuja Municipal and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja?
2. What are the tools used to access social media platforms among the youths in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja?
3. What activity does the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja predominantly do on social media platforms?
4. To what extent do the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja utilize social media platforms?
5. In what way does the use of social media platforms influence the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja?
6. What major challenge (if any) do the students face in the use of social media tool in the AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja?

METHODS

This study adopted quantitative survey research design to investigate the Influence of Social Media among youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of FCT, Abuja. Survey research was considered most appropriate in this study because it allows us to investigate the problem that has to do with eliciting large amount of data from the respondents in the study such as this. Through this design, we were also able to examine the “interrelationships among variables and to develop explanatory inferences” (Wimmer & Dominick, 2011, p.185) on the use of social media on youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja.

The population of this study comprised all the youth in Abuja Municipal Area Council and Bwari Area Council, FCT, Abuja. According to the statistics obtained from the Worldometre (2021), Abuja Municipal Area Council has a total of approximately 925,936 youths, while Bwari Area Council has 261,898 youths respectively. Put together, the sample size in this study was 1,187,834 youths.

The sample size of this study was 385 which was determined using an online based sample size determination software-*SurveyMonkey* (2021) under the confidence level of 95%, error margin of

5%, population proportion of 50% and population size of 1,187,834 (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/mp/sample-size-calculator/>). The sample size of this study was therefore 385.

This study adopted a multistage sampling technique in sampling respondents in the study. First, purposive sampling technique was used to select four towns from Abuja Municipal Area Council and three towns from the Bwari Area Council respectively. Consequently, seven major towns were sampled in the study. The reason purposive sampling technique was used than others was to enable towns that were more prominent and have more population of youths.

Thereafter, proportionate sampling technique was adopted using the following formula to select respondents proportionate to the population size of each area thus:

$$\frac{S \times n}{N}$$

Where;

S = Size of area

N = Sample Size

N = Total Population of the study

The proportionate sampling was done using the above formula as follows:

$$AMAC \frac{925936}{1187834} \times \frac{385}{1} = 300$$

$$Bwari \text{ Area Council } \frac{261898}{1187834} \times \frac{385}{1} = 85$$

This means that 300 youths were sampled in Abuja Municipal Area Council and 85 from Bwari Area Council, Abuja. In all, 385 youths were sampled in the study.

Descriptive was used as method of data analysis in this study. Thus, data collected were analyzed through the use of univariate frequency distribution tables and simple percentages. SPSS was used as statistical tool for data analysis to avoid the mistakes arising from manual calculations.

RESULTS

Table 1: Social Media Platform often used by Youth in Abuja Municipal and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja

<u>Response</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Extent youths are aware of the Social Media Platforms available for use in Abuja Municipal and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja		
To a great extent	312	86.43
To a little extent	41	11.36
Difficult to say	8	2.22
Total	361	100

Social Media Platform often used by youths in Abuja Municipal and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja

Facebook	127	35.18
Instagram	57	15.79
WhatsApp	69	19.11
Twitter	23	6.37
LinkedIn	19	5.26
Pinterest	5	1.39
Snapchat	7	1.94
YouTube	21	5.82
TikTok	3	0.83
Telegram	16	4.71
Others	14	4.99
Total	361	100

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

Research Question 1: What are the Social Media Platforms often used by youths in Abuja Municipal and Bwari Area Councils, Abuja?

Table 1 is concerned with social media platform often used by youth in Abuja municipal and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja. Data revealed that majority (86.43%) of the respondents sampled in the study were aware of the social media platforms available for use in their area to a great extent compared to the minority (11.36%) of them who were aware but to a little extent, and another minority (2.22%) who found it difficult to say, implying

that youth in Abuja municipal and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja is very much aware of the social media platforms available for use in the area.

Similarly, majority (35.18%) of the respondents make use of facebook more often compared to other social media platforms compared to WhatsApp by 19.11%, Instagram by 15.79%, Twitter (6.37%), LinkedIn (5.26%), Pinterest (1.39%), Snapchat (1.94%), YouTube (5.82%), TikTok (0.83%), Instagram (4.71%).

It implies therefore, Facebook is a social media platform that the youth often use for their different purposes.

Table 2: Tools that youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja make use of in accessing

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
the Social Media		
Tools for Accessing Social Media platforms among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area		
Laptop	55	15.24
Desktop	17	4.71
Palmtop	43	11.91
Mobile Phone	172	47.65
Ipad	61	16.90
Others	13	3.60
Total	361	100

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Tool more Convenient in Accessing Social Media platforms among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area

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Laptop	41	11.36
Desktop	15	4.16
Palmtop	23	6.37
Mobile Phone	159	44.04
Ipad	123	34.07
Total	361	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Research Question 2: What are the tools used to access Social Media platforms among the youths in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils, Abuja?

Table 2 contains responses on tools that the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja utilizes to access social media platforms. Data revealed that 15.24% out of 361 respondents sampled in the study said Laptop was the tool they use in accessing the social media platforms, 4.71% use Desktop, 11.91% use Palmtop, 47.65% use Mobile Phone, 16.90% use Ipad, and 3.60% use tools other than those mentioned here. It was further revealed that among the tools used in accessing social media platforms, 11.36% out of the total respondents sampled preferred Laptop, 4.16% respondents preferred Desktop, 6.37% respondents preferred Palmtop, 44.04% respondents preferred Mobile Phone, and 34.07% preferred Ipad.

The implication of the above data is that mobile phone is the major tool used in accessing social media platforms among youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja because they found the tool (mobile phone) more convenient for use compared to Laptop, Desktop, Palmtop, and Ipad respectively.

Table 3: Activity that youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja do more on Social Media

<u>Variable</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Extent youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja is aware of the activities carried out on social media platforms		
To a great extent	351	97.23
To a little extent	7	1.94
Difficult to say	3	0.83
<u>Total</u>	<u>361</u>	<u>100</u>
Activities most Performed on Social Media among youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja		
Posting personal Video	67	18.56
Posting personal Audio	43	11.91
Posting personal Photos	95	26.32
Viewing Peoples' Posts	32	8.86
Sharing information on academic activities	11	3.05
Sharing marketing information	34	9.42
Commenting on peoples' posts	21	5.82
Find followers	31	8.59
Follow others	27	7.48
<u>Total</u>	<u>361</u>	<u>100</u>

Activities other users carry out on social media

Self promotion	161	44.60
Marketing	107	29.64
Academic activities	11	3.05
Finding dating partners	67	18.56
Others	15	4.16
<u>Total</u>	<u>361</u>	<u>100</u>

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Research Question 3: What activity does the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja do more on Social Media.

Table 3 is concerned with activity the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja do on social media. Data revealed that 97.23% out of the respondents sampled in the study were to a great extent recognized the activities perform on social media, 1.94% out of the respondents recognized such activities to a little extent, while 0.83% out of the respondents found it difficult to comment; 18.56% of them use social media for posting personal video, 11.91% for posting personal Audio, 26.32% for posting personal photos, 8.86% out of the respondents make use of the social media for viewing peoples' posts, 3.05% of them make use of the social media for sharing information on academic activities, 9.42% for sharing marketing information, 5.82% for commenting on peoples' posts, 8.59% for finding followers, and 7.48% out of the respondents make use of the social media to follow others. Furthermore, 44.60% out of the 361 respondents sampled in the study observed that self promotion

is what they see others do on social media most, 29.64% out of the respondents said it was marketing they see other people do most on social media, 3.05% said academic activities, 18.56% said finding dating partners, while 4.16% said they see people do other things on the social media.

This implies therefore that the use of social media for academic activities is not a major priority among the youth as posting personal photos and video are the predominant activities they do on the social media. As a result, self promotion followed by marketing are the activities users predominantly do on social media.

Table 4: Extent the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja make use of the Social Media Platforms

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Frequency to which youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja make use of the Social Media Platforms		
More than twice a day	213	59.00
Once a day	71	19.67
More than twice a week	31	8.59
Once a week	17	4.71
More than twice in two weeks	13	3.60
Once in two weeks	9	2.49
More than twice in one month	5	1.39
Once in the month	2	0.55
Total	361	100
Extent others utilize social media in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja		
To a great extent	283	78.39
To a little extent	71	19.67
Difficult to say	7	1.94
Total	361	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Research Question 4: To what extent do the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of FCT, Abuja utilize Social media platforms?

Table 4 is concerned with the extent to which the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja utilize social media. Data revealed that 59.00% out of the respondents sampled make use of the social media at least more than twice a day, 19.67% of the respondents do so at least once a day, 8.59% out of the respondents make use of the social media more than twice a week, 4.7% of the respondents make use of the platform at least once a week, 3.60% out of the respondents do so more than twice in two weeks, 2.49% out of the respondents do so once in two weeks, 1.39% out of the respondents do so more than twice in one month, while 0.55% out of the respondents Once in the month. As a result, 78.39% out of the 361 respondents sampled in the study believed that social media was used by users to a great extent, 19.67% to a little extent and 1.94% found it difficult to comment. It implies therefore that social media is used among youth to great extent as majority of them make use of the platforms at least more than twice a day.

Table 5: The way the use of social media platforms influence the behaviour of youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Time of the day youth mostly make use of the social media		
Morning	31	8.59
Afternoon	25	6.93
Evening	109	30.19
Night	196	54.29
Total	361	100

Ways Social Media influence the behaviour of youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT		
Brilliant performance in academics	15	4.16
Flamboyant lifestyle	197	54.57
Strong sexual desire/feeling	71	19.67
Sound knowledge of current affairs	19	5.26
Time consciousness	41	11.36
Brilliant business ideas	13	3.60
Others	5	1.39
Total	361	100

Extent use of the social media influence the behaviour of youth		
To a little extent	273	75.62
To a great extent	79	21.88
Difficult to say	9	2.49
Total	361	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Research Question 5: In what ways does the use of Social Media platforms influences they yours in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of FCT, Abuja?

Table 5 is concerned with the way the use of social media platforms influence the behaviour of youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja. Data revealed that 9.70% preferred making use of the social media during morning time, 7.48% respondents preferred doing so in the afternoon, 32.41% preferred doing so in the evening, while 50.42% respondents preferred doing their so in the night; 4.16% out of the respondents were of the opinion that the use of social media influence the behaviour of youth by making them perform brilliant performance in academics, 54.57% out of the respondents said social media influenced their behaviour by making them live flamboyant lifestyle, 19.67% out of the respondents said it to have strong sexual desire/feeling, 5.26% out of the respondents were of the opinion that it makes them to have sound knowledge of current affairs, 11.36% said it helps them to be time conscious, 3.60% out of the respondents were of the opinion that it helps Brilliant business ideas, while 1.39% out of the respondents said the social media influence in other ways not mentioned here. Furthermore, data revealed that 75.62% out of the respondents sampled believed social media influence them to a great extent, 21.88% out of the total respondents believed that the use of social media influence them to a little extent, while 2.49% of the respondents found it difficult to comment.

This implies that social media influence the behaviour of youth to a great extent by making them cultivate the habit of living a flamboyant lifestyle.

Table 6: Major Challenge (if any) in the use of social media among youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Respondents' Knowledge of encountering major challenge in the use of social media platform		
Yes	361	100
No	0	0
Total	361	100

Major challenge in the use of the Social Media among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja

Unstable power supply	61	16.90
High data charges	134	37.12
Poor Network	92	25.48
Activities of Internet scammers	57	15.79
Others	17	4.71
Total	361	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Research Question 6: What major challenge (if any) do the youths face in their use of Social Media tools in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of FCT?

Table 6 is concerned with the major Challenge in the use of social media tool among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja. Data revealed that 100% of the respondents who make use of the social media encountered major challenge(s) as 16.90% out of the 361 respondents sampled in the study encountered the challenge of Unstable power supply in the use of the social media, 37.12% out of the respondents encountered challenge of high data charges, 25.48% of the respondents encountered challenge of poor network, 15.79% out of the respondents encountered challenge of Internet scammers, while 4.71% respondents encountered other challenges.

This implies that high data charges from the network providers followed by poor network are the major challenges in the use of social media among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of the FCT, Abuja, while unstable power and activities of Internet scammers are other challenges in the use of the social media among the students.

FINDINGS

Based on the research questions answered, the following are the major findings of the study:

Facebook is the social media platform that the youth often use for different purposes. This implies that Facebook endears the youth more than other social media platforms available. This finding agrees with finding from the study conducted by Boyd (2007) which indicated that Facebook utterly dominates social networking use among teens. 68% of all teens say Facebook is their main social networking site compared to 6% for Twitter, 1% for Google Plus, and 1% for MySpace, while 25% don't have a social networking site.

Mobile phone is the major tool used in accessing social media platforms among youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja because they found the tool (mobile phone) more convenient for use compared to Laptop, Desktop, Palmtop, and Ipad respectively. This is evident in table three where majority (47.65%)

proportion of the respondents said they access social media through their mobile phones compared to others and another majority (44.04%) proportion of the respondents who found mobile phone more convenient for use in accessing the social media compared to other tools as mentioned above. The implication of this finding is that mobile phone is handier in accessing the social media among the youth compared to other tools like the Laptop, Desktop, Palmtop and Ipad.

Another finding of the study is that posting personal photos and video are the activities carried out more on social media among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Councils of the FCT, Abuja. As a result, self promotion followed by marketing are the activities users predominantly do on social media. This is evident in the majority proportion of 26.32% who attested they made use of social media for posting personal photos and another 18.56% who said they use it for posting personal video as compared to 11.91% for posting personal Audio, 8.86% for viewing peoples' posts, 3.05% for sharing information on academic activities, 9.42% for sharing marketing information, 5.82% for commenting on peoples' posts, 8.59% for finding followers, and 7.48% for following others.

Finding also revealed that social media is used among youth to a great extent as majority of them make use of the platforms at least more than twice a day. This is evident in table five where majority (59.00%) proportion of the respondents said they make use of the social media at least twice in a day and another majority (78.39%) proportion of the respondent believed that social media was used to a great extent. The implication of this finding is that social media is embraced by majority of the youth for use on a daily basis. This finding agrees with the finding from the study conducted by Boyd (2007) which indicated that 90% of all teens have used social media, three-quarter of them have a social networking site, and nearly one in three teens visit their social networking profile several times a day or more. According to Boyd (2007), almost all teenagers in America and all parts of the world today have used social media. Nine out of 10 (90%) 13- to 17year-olds have used some form of social media. Three out of four (75%) teenagers currently have a profile on a social networking site, and one in five (22%) has a current Twitter account (27% have ever used Twitter).

Another finding of the study is that social media influence the behaviour of youth to a great extent by making them cultivate the habit of living a flamboyant lifestyle. This is evident in table 6 where 54.57% out of the respondents said social media influenced their behaviour by making them live flamboyant lifestyle. The implication of this finding is that the use of social media influence the negative behaviour compared influencing their positive one.

Furthermore, finding revealed that high data charges from the network providers followed by poor network are the major challenges in the use of social media among the youth in AMAC and Bwari Area Council of FCT, Abuja, while unstable power and activities of Internet scammers are other challenges in the use of the Instagram among the students. This is evident in table seven where majority (37.12%) proportion of the respondents said they encountered challenge of high data charges in the use of the social media and 25.48% of the respondents who said they encountered the challenge of poor network. The implication of this finding is that youths' utilization of the social media is challenged by some factors that can limit them in achieving a complete success in the use of the platforms if not addressed.

CONCLUSION

Social media platforms are used among youth to a great extent as majority of them make use of the platforms at least more than twice a day. In the use of the platforms, Facebook endears the youth more for use compared to other social media platforms. The use of social media, therefore, influences the behaviour of youth to a great extent by making them cultivate the habit of living a flamboyant lifestyle. In making use of the platforms, mobile

phone is the major tool used in accessing social media among youth because they found the tool (mobile phone) more convenient for use compared to Laptop, Desktop, Palmtop, and Ipad respectively. Posting personal photos and video become the major activities carried out more on social media among the youth. However, the use of social media is challenged majorly by high data charges from the network providers followed by poor network, while unstable power and activities of Internet scammers are other challenges in the use of the social media among the youth.

Furthermore, social media is used among the youth and its utilization by this group of the people has tremendous impact on their behaviour.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are recommended in the study:

- i. Policy makers should benefit from the youth's interest in the social media in general and the Facebook in particular by using the platforms in reaching out to the youth on relevant policies/programmes that can impact positively on their lives in particular and the society in general.
- ii. The use of social media should be continued among the youth since there is no problem with its usage but the purpose and essence to which it is used that can determine its success or otherwise.
- iii. Youth must dedicate more time on the social media for the activities beneficial to them rather than merely posting personal photos and videos which have minimal impacts on their lives.
- iv. Youth should make maximum opportunity from the frequency they utilize the social media in focusing more on gainful activities while on the platforms to enable them reap maximum benefits of the usage on their lives.
- v. Youth should always confirm posts on the social media also what they post so that they are not easily influenced by what is not authentic but it is posted on the social media.
- vi. To achieve significant success in the use of the social media among the youth, network providers should reduce the data charges for students in addition to making the network more stable to encourage them more in the use of the platform for academic activities.

Suggestions for Further Study

Based on the scope of this study, the following are suggested for further study:

- i. Similar study should be carried out to cover the entire area councils in Abuja to make the generalization of the findings and recommendations possible on all the area councils in Abuja.
- ii. A comparative study of the influence of social media platforms should be carried out to determine which of them is utilized more and the one that influences their behaviour more.

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